

“FORMING GROUP WORK”

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The formation group work depends on three deciding factors. The deciding factors are the task demands, the resources in the group, and the group processes. The task demands depend on three aspects; they are whether the problem is devisable or unitary. The term devisable refers to whether the problem can be divided into smaller parts amongst the group members. On the other hand, we refer to a problem as unitary, unitary means that the problem is not dividable amongst the group members ana that only one person can work on it. The second aspect deals with the group’s achievement and the third aspect deals with resources and how they exchange the ideas they have researched or came up with. In this aspect, it deals with time and how they used their time and also deals with how much effort they have put into their work. The second factor deals with resources and all the necessary resources that they have to get the project done. The third factor is the group processes and this deals

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this article is to learn the structure and factors of forming group work. Besides that, it is based on learning four group work stages. The information in the article can be used for the best part of learning style .

with the necessary steps taken by group members when they face a difficult problem.

In order to create the work within the group, the group goes through a cycle which involves four stages. The stages are listed as the following according to Richards.

a) Forming – In this stage, the group members come together and meet for the first time. This is the part where teacher introduces them to their task and what is expected of them as a group.

b) Norming – In this stage, after the group has come together. The group begins to exchange ideas, thoughts, values, and opinions. The group leader also sets ground rules for the group members in order to run a smooth project. The teacher also plays a vital role in group work. He has the role of encouraging pupils to work toward their goal and keeps them moving in the right direction.

c) Storming- In the third stage, which is the storming part. The group is working together to complete a task. In this stage , problems will arise due to the different ideas

brought to the table by different people. In life it is only nature for people to disagree because each person was created differently and everyone has a different thought in his head. The teacher can prevent this from happening by playing the role of peer mediator which comes between the pupils and guides them in the right path.

d) Performing- it is the final stage of group work, after the group shares their ideas. The group is now ready to work on the project and complete their task. The teacher as usual is the person in charge of motivating, encouraging, and keeping the pupils focused on their task.

These stages can be faced by the pupils if work in groups on long-time projects, like my pupils performed during the third term of this year.

According to the requirements of this project they needed to make video about exciting tour for foreign tourists around Tashkent. Pupils worked in groups of four or five. And so they should have divided their tasks into all members of team. It was not so simple process for them. They met some difficulties in organizing their work on project. But going through these steps made them improve their skills in a few areas, such as socializing to each other in working process, using different technologies and of course English speaking skills. That why I strongly believe that such way of teaching provides teachers a chance to gain a lot of benefits in their work on development of pupils' abilities. That is main and the most desiring aim for all teachers, I think.

Group work benefits for pupils:

What is more important in the process of language learning than speaking? Not much. Putting ESL pupils in groups gets them speaking up and practicing the language that they are trying to learn. Speaking is an important skill, and producing

out loud language can be intimidating for nonnative speakers at any point in their journey. The intimidation can be minimized by including group work from the very start of your classes. When your pupils start speaking in their ESL classes, it becomes a natural part of who they are and now they learn, and it fails to be an intimidating feat to delay until later in their studies.

1. Pupils help each other

When group work happens, whether it is in the work place or the classroom, collaboration is part of the process. When the pupils work in groups they help each other learn. Pupils can answer language specific questions or clarify confusing points of English in ways that pupils can understand and the teacher may not be able to explain. When they help each other, it benefits both of the pupils involved. The pupil with the question will have it answered, and the pupil with the answer will remember it better because they have taught it to another.

2. Pupils challenge each other.

Pupils will be intentional about helping each other when they work in groups, but they may not realize that they will challenge each other as well.

Studies show that speakers modify their speech to be more like the people to whom they are talking. That means less accomplished pupils will become better speakers just by talking to others more advanced than them, without help and without pressure.

3. Pupils encourage each other.

Encouragement between language learners can happen in many ways. One way encouragement comes is when lower pupils see the accomplishments of higher level pupils. When pupils share their experiences as well, one pupil's story becomes a blueprint for success for the other!

4. Pupils use language creatively

Communicative classrooms focus on getting pupils to use the language they know to get their meaning across. This is when creative language happens. Creative use of language makes communication possible even when speakers may not know the perfect grammar for what they are trying to say, and nothing is more true to life than that. When pupils work in groups, they have to work together to accomplish a goal. Even when grammar takes a backseat in these collaborations, communication happens, and that will give pupils a dry run for when they have to face communication in the English speaking world.

Group work benefits for teachers.

Group work activates different learning styles. Part of teaching is reaching as many different learning styles as possible. One of those learning styles is social, also known as interpersonal. Pupils who learn this way work well with others and benefit from working things out with groups. When teacher assigns group work and give pupils goals to accomplish during their time together, these pupils flourish.

It can be hard for teachers to assess speaking performance in their pupils. Putting pupils in groups and unobtrusively listening to them is a perfect way to see how much they are really putting to use. Teacher can hear pronunciation, spoken grammar, and ability to communicate just by listening in on some classroom work.

Teachers can know what their pupils are getting and what teachers need to clarify. When grammar is taught in isolation, it is easy for pupils to follow a pattern and fill in the blanks. When teacher has pupils working together, talking together, using the right grammar is not as predictable as it is in isolated exercises. When teacher listens to

pupils' performance during group work, it can be seen what concepts they are not getting and that may be needed to explain again. If teacher is unsure whether they have really understood a particular language strategy, he should assign a group task that will elicit it and listen closely.

How to set up group work

Group work is flexible, communicative, and can take as little or as much as teacher wants it to. Here some useful steps to make group work right:

Pre- teach the vocabulary pupils will need for the task.

No matter what topic teacher is covering in the group assignments, the odds are that pupils will need some task specific vocabulary to complete their work. So it might be really useful to teach some words which pupils can use during the group activity.

Review any necessary grammar structures pupils will be using during their discussion.

Like with vocabulary, pupils may need certain grammatical knowledge to complete the task they are assigned. They might need to use the imperative form to give instructions to a classmate, or they may need to use the conditional structure to talk about what might happen if they find themselves in certain circumstances. Whatever the grammatical need, teacher should take a few minutes at the beginning of the class to cover it with pupils so they will have the tools they need at their disposal for the group assignment.

To sum up, group working is very effective because it is just natural part of language class. In fact, pupils receive many benefits from forking in groups as they study English and language fluency. Group working is based on vocabulary, grammar, writing, listening and undoubtedly speaking practice.

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